

Unlocking the Path Towards AI-Native Networks with Optimized Lightweight Large Language Models

Georgios Samaras*, Marinela Mertiri*, Maria-Evgenia Xezonaki*,

Vasileios Theodorou*, Panteleimon Konstantinos Chartsias*, Theodoros Bozios*

*Intracom Telecom, Greece; Email: {gsamaras, marmert, maxez, theovas, chkopa, tmpo}@intracom-telecom.com

Abstract—In the rapidly advancing era of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Large Language Models (LLMs) have emerged as a pivotal force, revolutionizing the automated creation of diverse content. At the same time, Machine Learning (ML), particularly Deep Learning (DL), has achieved state-of-the-art (SoTA) performance in optimization and inference tasks across various domains, including telecommunications. However, the division of technological domains poses challenges to the integration of powerful AI/ML capabilities towards realizing the vision of “AI-native” networks, such as future 6G networks, aiming to offer ubiquitous intelligence across their infrastructure and service planes, seamlessly adapting and evolving to support new application classes. The paper proposes a novel out-of-the-box framework, TimesLM, for automated time series analytics, which is particularly useful for the Edge-Cloud orchestration framework CODECO, leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs). It addresses the challenge of developing general-purpose solutions by utilizing lightweight LLMs as forecasters and optimizers. TimesLM offers zero-shot and few-shot inference capabilities, enabling confident uncertainty navigation for decision-making in AI-Native networks. Its architecture integrates global optimization with lightweight LLMs, followed by input enrichment and local prompt optimization. Evaluation results on diverse real-world datasets demonstrate improved accuracy and reduced latency, making TimesLM highly competitive against SoTA approaches, while reducing operational costs and carbon-footprint. A limitations analysis is also presented. The proposed framework stands as a promising and sustainable step towards realizing the envisioned capabilities of AI-Native networks through LLM-powered time series analytics.

Index Terms—Generative Artificial Intelligence, Automated Machine Learning, Internet of Things, Network Automation, 6G, AI-Native, Big Data.

I. INTRODUCTION

Forecasting is an intrinsic aspect of life, with humans constantly seeking to comprehend uncertainty and predict future events, from ancient times, such as the Oracle of Delphi, to modern times, where for instance COVID-19 lockdowns were announced based on epidemiological predictions, having a global effect [1]. Time series are chronologically ordered data that can be found as central pillars of industries and institutions, with Time Series Forecasting (TSF) and Anomaly Detection being crucial in the Communications domain [2], [3]. Driven by their successful performance in renowned competitions [4] and large-scale capabilities across various industrial tasks, Deep Learning (DL) models have become a prominent research area.

A plethora of DL approaches are focused on developing dataset-specific ML models, i.e. the same dataset is used for

both training and testing. Moreover, the overwhelming majority of these solutions are not general-purpose models, meaning that they are designed to solve a specific problem with a fixed set of parameters, such as number of features, forecasting horizon, topology information and more. For example, in the novel Edge-Cloud orchestration framework CODECO [5], focusing on data-compute-network, the topology of the network is dynamic and the forecasting horizons vary, in order for the components of the framework to make more informed decisions. As a result, general-purpose approaches can greatly benefit such AI/ML-powered frameworks.

The breakthrough of foundation models has sparked a paradigm shift in ML. These large-scale neural networks are general-purpose and pre-trained in an unsupervised fashion on web-scale heterogeneous datasets of various domains. Foundation models have remarkable few-shot generalization capabilities [6]. LLMs belong in this category and recently gained immense popularity [7], often outperforming dataset-specific models. LLMs can be leveraged for time series analytics, too.

Offering LLM-powered time series analytics allows for confident uncertainty navigation for decision-making. It addresses the complexity of developing real-time resource monitoring and network infrastructure management, essential for efficient resource allocation and enhanced performance in modern applications [8]. Furthermore, AI-based network traffic forecasting can help the telecommunication operators reduce network outages by predicting congestions ahead of time and proactively reroute traffic through alternative paths [9]. This approach also addresses anomaly detection for proactive monitoring in Internet of Things (IoT) applications, such as server room temperature monitoring, to prevent costly damages. The combination of big data analytics and predictive insights highlights their pivotal role in shaping future AI-Native networks.

This paper proposes novel forms of time series analytics by leveraging LLMs to enable automated zero-shot TSF and anomaly detection. Additionally, we propose LLMs as prompt optimizers to enable more informed strategic decisions and adapt to any particular domain. The intention of this work is to provide the Communications community with a lightweight framework based on LLMs, an exploration of their behavior at scale and push the limits of knowledge transferability across heterogeneous domains, enabling the next wave of time series focused LLM innovations. In this sense, the contribution of this

work is four-fold:

- A novel Automated ML (AutoML) framework is presented, equipped with lightweight Responsible AI LLMs and able to provide general-purpose intelligence and data-driven prediction capabilities;
- A tailored for time series zero-touch prompt-optimizer that uses LLMs as the optimizer;
- An in-depth zero-shot and few-shot evaluation of our framework combined with prompt optimization, on unseen real world datasets.
- A current limitations analysis of our approach.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. Section II presents the related work. Section III presents the architecture of our approach. Evaluation results are discussed in Section IV, followed by a limitations analysis in Section V, while conclusion remarks and future work are presented in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

The concept of universal forecasting envisions a single model or framework, capable of handling heterogeneous downstream forecasting tasks. DL traditionally has an one-model-per-dataset approach, limiting its potential on leveraging the game-changing impact of large pre-trained models. Despite the success of these models in domains such as computer vision, the field of time series analytics employing large pre-trained models remains an area not yet adequately explored. Time Generative Pre-trained Transformer (TimeGPT) [10], the first foundation model for time series, was trained on a web-scale diverse dataset, offering zero-shot and few-shot prediction capabilities, outperforming statistical, ML and DL methods. Each observation is treated as a token, making the model predict the next token, i.e. the observation on the next time step, similar to LLMs predicting the next word in a phrase.

Time Series Foundation Model (TimesFM) [11] is an out-of-the-box zero-shot time series analysis model that shows a comparable performance to SoTA dataset-specific supervised ML models. TimesFM is a patched-decoder attention model, pre-trained on a large time series corpus, comprised of real and synthetic datasets, providing forecasts of previously unseen datasets. Masked EncOder-based UnIveRsAI Time Series Forecasting Transformer (MOIRAI) [12] is an enhanced model, designed to overcome challenges that arise from developing a time series foundation model, such as cross-frequency learning and varying distributional properties. It has been trained on a web-scale dataset spanning across nine domains, demonstrating comparable or superior performance to full-shot models.

Lag-Large Language Model Meta AI (Lag-Llama) [13] that uses lags as covariates, and Chronos [14], that uses scaling and quantization for tokenization, are both transformer-based models that leverage the unprecedented zero-shot and few-shot generalization capabilities of foundation models to serve as a general-purpose probabilistic time series forecaster. The models are pre-trained on a large corpus of diverse datasets

across several domains and demonstrate zero-shot generalization capabilities on unseen datasets, which when combined with fine-tuning outperform SoTA DL approaches. Time Series Transformer (Timer) [15] is an LSTM-based model with a GPT-style architecture that offers time series analytics, such as TSF and anomaly detection, as a unified generative task. Timer is pre-trained by autoregressive next token prediction on large multi-domain datasets and offers fine-tuning capabilities.

A different direction from pre-training a global time series model from scratch is to employ knowledge transferability by using already pre-trained LLMs to provide predictive time series analytics, partly motivated by the lack of large training time series datasets [16]. Time-LLM [16] is a reprogramming framework that repurposes LLMs for time series analysis, leveraging the pattern recognition and reasoning capabilities of LLMs over complex sequences of tokens. The authors in [16] discuss the arisen challenges, such as different modalities, and use text prototypes to reprogram the input time series. The framework demonstrates few-shot and zero-shot capabilities, outperforming SoTA specialized DL models, when using a default environment of eight premium-tier GPUs (e.g. A100s).

LLM-TIME [17] method encodes time series as a string of numerical digits, framing TSF as next-token text prediction. It uses tokenization techniques and LLMs (e.g. GPT-3) to zero-shot extrapolate time series, with competitive or exceeding performance of purpose-built DL models. The authors highlight how using different LLMs affects accuracy performance, with larger models not necessarily leading to increased accuracy. LLMs have many parameters (for example GPT-3 has 175B parameters) and are particularly resource hungry & "thirsty" [18] models. For that reason smaller LLMs have been developed, such as Gemma [19], a relatively lightweight model based on Gemini models, succeeding in providing a version with only 2B parameters that demonstrates strong performance, aiming for safer AI applications with its Responsible Generative AI Toolkit, equipped with a Safety classification methodology.

Based on the above, in this work, a mechanism building on the joint use of LLMs and time series analysis is proposed to facilitate out-of-the-box zero/few-shot TSF and anomaly detection of unseen datasets on AI-Native networks. For the analytics realization, the lightweight Gemma model is used, supported by a proposed AutoML pipeline, showing the improved capabilities of stripped-down LLMs in IoT environments.

III. ARCHITECTURE

Our AutoML framework offers a zero/few-shot out-of-the-box pipeline, written in Python programming language, that provides general-purpose time series analytics on unseen data, encompassing TSF and anomaly detection. The intelligence of our framework comes from lightweight LLMs acting as optimizers and forecasters, leading to optimized Time series Lightweight large language Model (TimesLM) as the name of our approach. The main idea is that the user, who can be a

Fig. 1. TimesLM pipeline.

developer, is not required to have any ML expertise or domain knowledge in order to get access to high-quality AI analytics.

Although the only required parameter from the user is the dataset, our framework is flexible enough to support optional parameters, which could be used for example by an ML engineer user, such as accuracy metric thresholds for potential fine-tuning, forecasting horizon in the TSF case and interval width (sensitivity) in the anomaly detection case. Modularity was the guiding principle for developing this framework, allowing Generative AI scientists to seamlessly customize the framework with alternative or new LLMs. Our framework is future-proof in adapting to future LLMs because of the innovative prompt optimization functionality. A notable advantage of our approach is that although no training is required, the capability of fine-tuning is provided to allow for more informed strategic decisions and adapt to any particular and unseen domain.

The workflow of our framework, shown in Figure 1, incorporates elements of AutoML paradigms [20] about data preprocessing (e.g. rescaling). Initially, a pre-trained LLM is pulled and the input context is enriched with metadata (e.g. frequency). The data are then tokenized and transformed in a more LLM-friendly shape. Another pre-trained LLM is now used as an optimizer for fine-tuning the time series analytics model. Note that this optimization may be auto-detected unnecessary and skipped, resulting in a zero-shot model ready to be used; otherwise a few-shot model will be produced.

A. Global Optimization

TimesLM utilizes lightweight preset LLMs, which can unveil their full potential by global fine-tuning, i.e. one time only and before starting predicting any user-provided dataset. We Low Rank Adaptation (LoRA) fine-tune the smallest Gemma model with the Databricks Dolly 15k dataset [21], using a LoRA rank of 4 to determine the dimensionality of the

trainable matrices that are added to the original LLM weights, controlling the expressiveness and precision of the adjustments, and significantly reducing the number of trainable parameters from 2.5B to 1.3M. We use AdamW as the optimizer, while excluding layernorm and bias terms from weight decay. Now the pre-trained and globally optimized LLM is ready for zero-shot inference. Technologies used are Keras Natural Language Processing (KerasNLP) with Google JAX as the backend.

B. Data Preparation

TimesLM performs automatic data imputation to handle missing values, based on build-in strategies, like forward filling and padding. Automatic data down-rescaling is also supported, resulting in data with an α -percentile of one; particularly useful with large input values that may waste LLM tokens.

In order to augment the input context with information that could potentially improve performance, we compute the frequency, descriptive statistics (e.g. median), trend and lags of the time series data. Trend is the sign of the sum of differences between consecutive elements in the list and lags are calculated with the Fast Fourier Transform method, obtaining the correlation in the time domain and finding the top-k lags based on mean correlation values, with k set to 5.

Tokenization is performed by space-separating the digits and using a comma to separate each data observation. TimesLM is designed to be as lightweight as possible in the context of LLMs, able to run efficiently on free-tier GPUs (e.g. P100 and T4), commonly found in hosting services online. For that reason we control the memory usage and drop redundant decimal points to save on input sequence length [17]. We fix the precision at 3, which for instance tokenizes the data like this:

0.123, 1.23, 12.3 \rightarrow “ 1 2 3 , 1 2 3 0 , 1 2 3 0 0 ”

C. Local Optimization

TimesLM performs zero-shot inference with no local optimization. However, some unseen data and domains may behave differently than others depending on the input prompt [17]. In order to address these challenges, we introduce a novel technique, called Local Prompt Optimization (LPO), for fine-tuning the prompt of LLMs that offer time series analytics, using an LLM as the optimizer [22].

The LPO framework, shown in Figure 2, receives the input data and constructs an initial meta-prompt, which is then passed to the optimizer that does nothing in the first pass. The meta-prompt is given as input to the time series analytics LLM, which generates a prediction. The accuracy of this prediction is evaluated and if the accuracy score is sufficient, then the model is ready to be used, meaning that zero-shot inference meets the accuracy requirements. Otherwise, the meta prompt is enhanced with the accuracy results and passed to the optimizer, which in turn enriches the task description, and feeds the time series analytics LLM with the new meta prompt, memorizing the accuracy results and deciding on whether to include the latest

Fig. 2. An overview of the LPO framework. Given the meta-prompt as the input, the LLM generates a new prediction to the accuracy evaluator, then the new prediction and its score are added into the meta-prompt for the next optimization step. The meta-prompt contains the prediction-score pairs obtained throughout the optimization process, as well as an NLP description of the ML task and in prompt optimization a few exemplars from the ML task.

enrichment or not, using the accuracy difference, if any, as the criterion. The loop continues until the optimizer crafts a meta-prompt that yields sufficient accuracy, which will be returned as the top performing prompt. Typically the loop iterations are a few, resulting in few-shot model ready for time series analytics.

We use the fine-tuned Gemma presented in Section III-A for the LLM optimizer and forecaster, Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) as the accuracy evaluator and empirically acquired (through experimentation) accuracy thresholds for determining performance sufficiency. The meta-prompt follows the same principle as in [22] and starts like this: “You are an effective optimizer. I have some predictions along with their corresponding scores. The predictions are arranged in descending order based on their scores, where lower scores indicate better accuracy.”.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section details the thorough evaluation of the TimesLM framework, focusing on zero-shot and few shot inference, and the effectiveness and latency of its global and local fine-tuning capabilities. It also presents the anomaly detection evaluation, focusing on detection performance.

A. Global Optimization

TimesLM is a lightweight framework, designed to run on free-tier GPUs. For that reason, we use the smallest available preset Gemma model, as described in Section III-A, to drastically reduce the minimum resource requirements for using our framework. As a consequence, performing a global optimization before starting predicting provides improved accuracy, as shown in Figure 3a, where LoRA fine-tuning results in a 1.94 times sparse categorical accuracy improvement. Even though this dataset-agnostic fine-tuning happens once, we also investigate the latency with two popular free-tier GPUs, namely P100 and T4. The results are shown in Figure 3b, demonstrating an average 2.51 times speedup with GPU P100 against T4.

(a) Sparse Categorical Accuracy (b) Latency

Fig. 3. Left: Sparse categorical accuracy with LoRA optimization. X axis is log-scaled. Right: Latency of LoRA optimization with P100 and T4 GPUs. X and Y axes are log-scaled.

Fig. 4. MAPE performance across fine-tuning steps. Note that zero fine-tuning steps corresponds to zero-shot inference; the rest are few-shot inference results.

B. Local Optimization

Our general-purpose framework is equipped with both zero-shot and few-shot inference capabilities, powered by its local optimization mechanism, allowing for specific domain/dataset adaptation. Adaptation may be required in situations where more strategic decisions need to be made, taking into account the lightweight nature of the LLM-intelligence that TimesLM brings into play. We evaluate our framework in a real-world server room dataset of temperature and humidity IoT measurements, with minute-based monitoring data of 9 hours and 15 minutes. As described in Section III-C, an LLM is used as the optimizer, producing more accurate predictions with each dataset-specific optimization step. The results are shown in Figure 4, where both zero-shot inference and few-shot inference performance is presented, showcasing a 1.11 times reduced error after only fifteen fine-tuning steps. Note that after this optimization step, the MAPE does not reduce significantly.

C. Prediction Accuracy

For prediction accuracy evaluation purposes, we are using two real-world traffic datasets, one for Content Delivery Network (CDN) [23] and one for 5G, as well as one synthetic resource infrastructure dataset. The CDN traffic anonymized dataset comes from an operational multimedia streaming deployment in US over 5G infrastructures, comprising of minute-based bandwidth measurements, edge cache hits and number of requests, with a size of 9 days and 7 hours. The 5G traffic dataset originates from a large 5G operator, consisting of the throughput (Mbps) in an Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) slice, with a size of 2.4 months, where each data is separated by a five-minute interval. The infrastructure resource usage dataset is simulated in an on-premises Edge-Cloud orchestration cluster. The minute-based dataset consists of four resource usage metrics, i.e. memory and Central Processing Unit (CPU) consumption, and received and transmitted throughput, and a total size of 8 days.

We thoroughly compare our framework with the SoTA full-shot Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) and Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series Forecasting (N-HiTS) models, running on CPU, and the zero-shot Time-LLM and LLMTime models, running on a premium-tier A100 GPU. For TimeGPT and TimesLM, we utilized the few-shot inference capabilities, running on a free-tier T4 GPU.

The results are shown in Figure 5, where for the Infrastructure dataset, TFT records the lowest error, TimesLM has the lowest error for zero/few-shot inference and Time-LLM has the highest error. In the CDN traffic case, LSTM performs best, with TimesLM having the highest error, which is however comparable to the zero/few-shot inference performance in this experimentation setting. In the 5G traffic dataset, N-HiTS achieves the best performance, with TimesLM performing best amongst zero/few-shot inference performance, even better than the full-shot LSTM. On average, TimesLM has 1.64 times higher MAPE than the top performing model. In general, our findings reproduce the latest literature results in the performance of dataset-agnostic foundation models coming close to dataset-specific SoTA DL models, or even outperforming them. Moreover, it is evident that TimesLM, despite being the most lightweight framework, is highly competitive or better in the foundation models category.

D. Effectiveness of the Anomaly Detection method

For the anomaly detection evaluation, we perform unsupervised learning and detect potential anomalies, by having TimesLM predict a range of values for the next time step. We then check if the actual value lies within this predicted range; if not, it is marked as an anomaly. A data set of temperature and humidity IoT measurements was used, as described in Section IV-B. In this evaluation, historical information is only used up to the current data point being processed. We later used the dataset as groundtruth to evaluate our approach. We

compare our approach to the anomaly detection of LSTM, as shown in Figure 6, where it is demonstrated that our approach successfully detected the anomalies, marked as red circles. The red circle's diameter length corresponds to the importance of the anomaly - useful for configuring alarm triggering, e.g. email notification vs. siren alarm device. The predicted future range values are colored green, while the observed temperature measurements appear as black dots. LSTM has increased sensitivity for lower bond anomalies in contrast to our approach, while the opposite is observed with upper bond anomalies. Notice that for visualization purposes, the humidity anomaly detection was omitted from the figure.

V. CURRENT LIMITATIONS

The introduction of a general-purpose lightweight AutoML framework that uses LLMs as forecasters and optimizers uncovers fascinating insights, aiming at helping researchers and applied scientists. However, it also shows the limitations of the current stage of this work. The framework is not suitable for Edge AI applications, since the focus was primarily on performance and generalization capabilities. Zero-shot inference requires no fine-tuning but may not achieve SoTA performance. However, the few-shot inference performance is highly competitive or better to cutting-edge foundation models, as well as full-shot models, which require training per each different data set. The memory usage of TimesLM is another limitation, which needs to be controlled in order to allow efficient execution in free-tier GPUs while analysing big data.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

Enabling automated time series analytics with general-purpose lightweight frameworks is a growing demand to realize the envisioned capabilities of AI-Native networks. Towards such a goal, this paper provides insights into the design and implementation of the TimesLM Responsible AI framework, which offers a comprehensive solution for addressing general-purpose time series analytics challenges in AI-Native networks and the CODECO Edge-Cloud orchestration framework. By integrating lightweight LLMs as forecasters and optimizers, TimesLM provides high-quality zero/few-shot inference capabilities, while reducing operating costs and carbon-footprint. Experimental real-world and synthetic evaluations confirm its effectiveness and potential for practical deployment, showcasing its ability to enhance the performance and capabilities of AI-Native networks. Current limitations are also discussed.

In terms of future work, there are several avenues for further exploration. Firstly, ongoing advancements in lightweight LLMs may provide opportunities for enhancing the TimesLM framework. Investigating and integrating emerging LLMs may further reduce minimum operational requirements and carbon-footprint, while achieving enhanced accuracy performance. Secondly, alternative cutting-edge fine-tuning methodologies and optimization algorithms can be incorporated to improve the performance of the system. Finally, additional research can

Fig. 5. Prediction MAPE for three datasets across zero-shot, few-shot and full-shot ML models.

Fig. 6. Anomaly detection with LSTM and TimesLM. Anomalies are marked red, predicted values range green and actual measurements black.

focus on expanding the range of input preparation techniques, by exploring different enrichment procedures and evaluating the performance in various AI-Native network environments.

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